

Subjective Assessment Experiments That Recruit Few Observers With Repetitions (FOWR)

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Abstract—Recent studies have shown that it is possible to characterize subject bias and variance in subjective assessment tests. Apparent differences among subjects can, for the most part, be explained by random factors. Building on that theory, we propose a subjective test design where four to six team members each rate the stimuli multiple times. The results are comparable to a high performing objective metric. This provides a quick and simple way to analyze new technologies and perform pre-tests for subjective assessment.

Index Terms—Subjective assessment, experiment design, video quality.

I. INTRODUCTION

INDUSTRY depends on video, image, and audio quality assessments when making important business decisions. Examples include optimizing video encoders, choosing video transmission bandwidths, fine tuning networks, and agreeing upon standard speech codecs for future cellular networks. The traditional options are to either conduct a subjective test or choose a well-established objective metric.

Both options have advantages and limitations [1]. Subjective tests are accurate but time-consuming. Objective metrics are inaccurate but fast. Moreover, metrics quickly become unreliable when applied to new technologies or scenarios outside of their intended scope. For example, a metric designed for broadcast video applications may yield random ratings when given user-generated content. Neither option meets the needs of a company to quickly assess new technologies during the research and development process.

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This paper proposes a compromise solution: a subjective test where four to six team members rate each stimulus multiple times. This would reduce costs associated with recruiting and handling subjects, shifting the work onto team members who are obliged to assist. Obvious quality impairments are easily spotted by all subjects (particularly experts), and novel technologies are not problematic. This compromise would provide a viable third option, as long as the accuracy lies somewhere between the accuracy of subjective test data and objective metric values. We have named the resulting test protocol FOWR: Few Observers With Repetitions.

In this paper, we will review previous studies of subject rating behaviors, which provide the theoretical basis for this proposal. We then present a subjective test that was designed to evaluate this FOWR experiment design. The conclusions reached by this test will be compared with conclusions reached by a test conducted with the traditional experiment design.

A. Related Work

The conventional experiment design is well described in the literature. In literature not related to video or audio quality a typical subjective experiment is called a within-subjects design. Details about analysis of such experiments can be found in classical literature from sociology like chapter 14 of [2].

We cannot take short-cuts when choosing stimuli. An illustrative example is Fig. 3 of [3]. Thirteen experiments conducted at various labs investigated the same issue: an equation that maps audio quality and video quality (measured separately) to the overall audiovisual quality (assessed jointly). Eight experiments used one or two source videos and reached disparate conclusions; five experiments used five to ten source videos and reached similar conclusions. Subjective and objective analyses are only reliable if care is taken when choosing media stimuli and impairments.

However, the number and nature of subjects are more open to discussion. The decision about the number of subjects should be based on so-called power analysis [4]. This analysis is simple for